

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Artemis HULC Commercial Off the Shelf Camera Heavy Ion Testing</i>
Project TA identifier	TA09-288
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
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Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Michael Campola, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center Jonathan Pryor, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center Brent Kennamer, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center Jacob Trull, NASA Marshall Space Flight Center</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	07/03/2025-08/03/2025
Facility	GSI
Amount of access granted	16 h

Objectives of the experiments

The Artemis Handheld Universal Lunar Camera (HULC) project is a Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) product developed through a Space Act between NASA and Nikon to capture digital imagery in the lunar environment. The HULC will be the primary camera used during Artemis III and out missions to capture events on the entire mission including on the lunar surface. Therefore, understanding its susceptibility is critical for NASA planning. Single Event Effects (SEE)s have been observed on this product and the objective of this experiment is to determine the probability of survivability during the mission times, and also to characterize the system response to SEEs in the lunar environment. Because this experiment focuses on the characterization of a system response as opposed to a unit response, not all SEEs are captured. This is because not all SEEs iterate through the system and create a noticeable response. Only SEEs that create a system response were captured and used in calculations. This experiment also demonstrated a methodology for COTS as described in the poster ***A Methodology for Cost Effective Radiation Characterization of COTS Hardware for Space Use***

Experiment test report

Test Setup

This test occurred at the GSI facility in Darmstadt, Germany, in March 2025. This facility has the capabilities to produce a single heavy ion beam at various energies. The ion selected for this test was gold (Au).

The beam at GSI is a non-normalized 5-mm elliptical beam. To complete irradiation, the beam will hover over a location until a target fluence is reached before moving to the next target area. It proceeds as a pencil beam over the device under test. The beam scans in this fashion across a maximum 5 cm x 5 cm square window until the total normalized fluence has been achieved for the test article. For this test, the target fluence for all items was $1e7$ ions/cm².

The beam was calibrated with three energies; 1 GeV, 500 MeV, and 270 MeV, which equates to three LETs of approximately 12.5, 15, and 20 MeVcm²/mg at the surface of the DUT. Further changes would have required additional time to calibrate and were not used for this test.

Table 0-1: Beam energies selected for Au ions and penetration depth in silicon

Extraction Energy [MeV/u]	Energy at DUT surface [MeV/u]	LET in Silicon [MeVcm²/mg]	Range in Silicon [mm]
270 MeV/u	248 MeV/u	20 MeVcm ² /mg	6.9 mm
500 MeV/u	483 MeV/u	15 MeVcm ² /mg	18.7 mm
1 GeV/u	986 MeV/u	12.4 MeVcm ² /mg	51.6 mm

Test Articles

There were a total of 10 test articles used for this test. The serial numbers and other identifiers will be captured in the full report. A summary of the articles is presented here.

1. One (1) Prograde Dual-Slot¹ USB3.2 card reader (PG05.5)
2. One (1) Prograde Single-slot USB4.0 card reader (PG05.6)
3. Three (3) Prograde 400GB CF Express Type B memory cards
4. Three (3) Nikon Z9 modified COTS cameras
5. Teradek Prism Mobile 4k60 HDR capable encoder

Test Summary

Prograde Dual-slot USB 3.2 card reader (PG05.5)

The Prograde CF Express dual-slot USB 3.2 card reader test setup involved copying images from the card to a location on the operator laptop while the reader was being radiated with the card removed from the beam by a CF Express card extender. The reader received a total fluence of $5.5e5$ ions/cm² from a 500-MeV beam with an LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg and experienced 24 SEEs. The test ended due to large number of SEEs providing difficulty to acquire a full data set. Results are inconclusive and an onset LET or survivability data cannot be established for this device. However, the rate of errors allowed a comparison to the PG05.6.

¹ The two slots include one CFexpress slot and one SD Card slot

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Prograde Single -slot USB 4.0 card reader (PG05.6)

The Prograde CF Express single-slot USB 4.0 card reader test setup involved copying images from the card to a location on the operator laptop while the reader was being radiated with the card removed from the beam by a CF Express card extender. The reader received a total fluence of $6e4$ ions/cm² from a 500-MeV beam with an LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg and experienced 12 SEEs, a rate 4 times faster than the PG05.5. The test was ended due to a large number of upsets occurring, making accurate data difficult to gather. Results are inconclusive and an onset LET or survivability data cannot be established for this device.

Prograde 400GB CF Express Storage card

The Prograde CF Express 400GB card test setup involved the DUT being radiated while images were stored on card during camera operation at 1 fps. Three total cards were tested with this method.

Card 1 received a total fluence of $1.2e6$ ions/cm² from a 500-MeV Au beam with an LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg. The test ended because the camera displayed the error "cannot access memory card" repeatedly on reset and the card could no longer store captured images.

Card 2 experienced the same failure from a 1 GeV beam with an LET of 12.5 after a total fluence of $2.75e6$ ions/cm² was achieved. Threshold LET for SEEs has not been established for this device.

Card 3 received the same beam as Card 2 and failed after a total fluence of $3.1e6$ ions/cm². Threshold LET for SEEs has not been established for this device.

All three of the failed cards were returned to the vendor to ensure data could still be recovered even though camera operation was halted because the cards could not be used. The vendor was able to find that the data inside all three of the cards was not damaged and was able to be recovered and returned to NASA for future review.

HULC Z9 Eyepiece

The eyepiece of the camera was radiated after removing as much obstructive material as possible around the eyepiece. All viewing glass and plastic was removed from the eyepiece lens and the eyepiece was operated with brightness set to the highest setting to maximize vulnerability to heavy ions by drawing maximum power. The device received a total fluence of $1e7$ ions/cm² at 500 MeV with an LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg, and a total fluence of $1e7$ ions/cm² at 270 MeV with an LET of 20 MeVcm²/mg without a failure. SEFI's were encountered but all were recoverable.

HULC Z9 Camera

Three total cameras were tested, with serial numbers 3900002, 3900009, and 3900005. They will be referred to as 2, 5, and 9. The cameras were radiated while being operated in photo mode, recording still images at 1 fps. Because of the limited beam size, the test was split into two sections, with the left side and right side being radiated at different times. Camera 2 received a fluence of $8.7e6$ ions/cm² on the right side, and a fluence of $5e6$ ions/cm² on the left side with a beam at 500 MeV with an estimated LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg. It then received a beam at 270 MeV on the right side and experienced a DSEE at a fluence of $1.3e6$ ions/cm² with an LET of 20 MeVcm²/mg.

Camera 5 received a 500-MeV beam with an LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg on the right-side electronics and experienced a DSEE at a fluence of $3.7e6$ ions/cm².

Camera 9 received a beam at 1 GeV with an LET of 12.5 MeVcm²/mg, on the left side electronics for a total fluence of $7.8e6$ ions/cm², then moved to the right side and it experienced a DSEE after a fluence of $2e6$ ions/cm².

This test set did not produce a known threshold LET for the camera systems due to the failures at lower levels on consecutive tests. Additional testing would be required to confirm the results of this test.

Teradek Prism Mobile

The Teradek encoder received a 500-MeV Au beam with an estimated LET of 15 MeVcm²/mg for a total fluence of 4.74e4 ions/cm² on the left side when viewed from the connector side of the board. Several SEEs occurred up to this fluence due to the location of the memory and the decision was made to move to the location with the most power ICs present. The right side of the encoder received the same beam up to a fluence of 3.36e4 ions/cm² where a DSEE occurred, and the encoder would not power on. A threshold LET was not able to be established to determine probability of failure due to not having a passing LET value.

HULC Conclusion

Nikon has evaluated the failed cameras and discovered that for all three cameras a failure occurred in the flash ROM. Previous heavy ion testing at NASA Space Radiation Lab (NSRL) established an onset LET for the system at 17.8. It was postulated that multiple failures occurred consecutively or concurrently in neighboring words of the ROM and occurred too quickly for ECC to be able to perform a correction. Such an error is outside of the realm of a Single Event Effect. Nikon efforts were able to fully recover the camera operation following a ROM reflash, however, this process is intensive and could not be re-created in the intended environment. A possible way to minimize the buildup of errors by continuous reflashes during the mission is being explored. However, the testing did provide greater confidence on some individual components which had failed at a lower LET during previous testing.

Table 0-1: Summary of test results data

DUT	LET Pass	LET Fail	Failed Fluence	Notes
Z9 Eyepiece	20	N/A	N/A	
Z9 SN #2	15	20	1.3e6	Right side electronics, no left side test @ 20
Z9 SN #5	N/A	15	3.7e6	Right side electronics, no left side test
Z9 SN #9	N/A	12.5	2e6	Right side electronics, left side passed 7.8e6 fluence
CF Express Card 1	N/A	15	1.2e6	Stills capture
CF Express Card 2	N/A	12.5	2.75e6	Stills capture

CF Express Card 3	N/A	12.5	3.1e6	Stills capture
Teradek Encoder	N/A	15	3.36e4	Right side electronics, power ICs
Flir IR camera	N/A	12.5	5e5	Inconclusive. Ended before failure
PG05.5 card reader	N/A	15	5.5e5	Inconclusive. Ended before failure. 24 SEEs
PG05.6 card reader	N/A	15	6e4	Inconclusive. Ended before failure. 12 SEEs.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other(Final planning for Artemis Mission)	X

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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